

Sustainable playground

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The world's energy resources (especially oil) are running out and this forces politicians to look for new resources. The need for finding sustainable energy calls for a general understanding of energy, not just among politicians but among all human beings.

Our vision is to give people a better understanding of what energy is and what it takes to produce it. To accomplish this we have turned our attention toward children and youngsters.

We wish to build a playground where the play equipment challenge and teach the children about energy. We want to give them an idea of what it takes to produce energy and through this, make them appreciate it, so that it might affect their daily use of energy.

We imagine our playground to contain play equipment that uses known technologies like solar energy, wind energy, water energy but mostly energy produced by physical action.

As an example we are constructing a roller (see the picture below) that converts the physical produced energy to lights, music and mains, where fx cell phone charging is possible.

Fig. 1: Roller